

Synthesis of Some 3-Methylisocoumarins

J. N. CHATTERJEA, C. BHAKTA & T. RADHA VAKULA

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-5

Received 18 December 1971, revised MSS received 8 August, 1972.

The double bond of isocoumarins when activated by a cyano or an alkoxy-carbonyl group at the 4-position adds diazomethane readily to yield pyrazolines convertible readily into 3-methylisocoumarins. The diazoketones derived from half-esters of homophthalic acids are readily converted by hot hydriodic acid into 3-methylisocoumarins. 8-Hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin, a natural metabolite, has been synthesised.

Several isocoumarins¹⁻³ isolated from various natural sources contain 3-methyl group. The earlier methods of preparing 3-methylisocoumarins are that of Gabriel *et al.*⁴ and Nogami⁵. Smith and Usgaonkar and their co-workers⁶⁻⁷ independently have developed a novel method involving the action of acetic anhydride and pyridine on homophthalic acids or their anhydrides but this method yield a variety of products depending on the reaction conditions. In the present communication, we record some reactions that led to the synthesis of 3-methylisocoumarins.

When isocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid (I) was allowed to react with excess of diazomethane and the resulting product was decomposed with warm acetic acid, it afforded 3-methyl-4-methoxycarbonylisocoumarin (II). On hydrolysis with a mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid and acetic acid a mixture of homophthalic acid and 3-methylisocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid (III) was obtained and the latter on decarboxylation with copper bronze

I, $R_1=R_2=H$, $R_3=COOH$

II, $R_1=H$, $R_2=CH_3$, $R_3=COOCH_3$

III, $R_1=H$, $R_2=CH_3$, $R_3=COOH$

IV, $R_1=R_3=H$, $R_2=CH_3$

V, $R_1=H$, $R_2=CH_3$, $R_3=COCH_2OAc$

VI, $R_1=H$, $R_2=CH_3$, $R_3=COCH_2OH$

VII, $R_1=H$, $R_2=CH_3$, $R_3=CH_2COOCH_3$

VIII, $R_1=H$, $R_2=CH_3$, $R_3=CH_2COOH$

IX, $R_1=R_2=H$, $R_3=CN$

X, $R_1=H$, $R_2=CH_3$, $R_3=CN$

XI, $R_1=OH$, $R_2=H$, $R_3=COCH_2OH$

XII, $R_1=OCH_3$, $R_2=H$, $R_3=COOH$

XIII, $R_1=OAc$, $R_2=H$, $R_3=COCl$

XIV, $R_1=OH$, $R_2=CH_3$, $R_3=H$

XV, $R_1=H$, $R_2=R_3=CH_3$

XVI, $R_1=OH$, $R_2=R_3=CH_3$

provided 3-methylisocoumarin (IV). The mass spectrum of (II) had an intense molecular ion peak at m/e 218. Other ions of moderate intensity corresponded to peak at m/e 203, 190, 187 and 175. Its N.M.R. spectrum showed two singlets at τ 6.0 and 7.5 due to the methyl ester (COOCH_3) and 3-methyl group (CH_3) respectively. The 3-methyl group results from the attack of diazomethane at the double bond between 3 and 4-positions. The reaction of an activated double bond with diazomethane leading to a methyl substituted product have also been observed by Fieser *et al.*⁸ and Elderfield *et al.*⁹ Conjugate addition of diazomethane to the normal diazoketone of the acid chloride of (I) may yield the pyrazoline (XVII). On treatment with acids, such as acetic acid, nitrogen may easily be lost from it leading to (V) or (XIX) or a mixture of both. Actually (V) was obtained; cyclopropane derivatives were not isolated by us in the present studies although Mori *et al.*¹⁰ have isolated some of them under similar circumstances.

The acid (I) yielded (VII) when subjected to Arndt-Eiestert reaction. The ester (VII) was hydrolysed to the acid (VIII). The mass spectrum of (VIII) showed a strong molecular ion peak at m/e 218. Other ion fragments of moderate intensity corresponded to m/e 190, 173, 145 and 131. 3-Methyl-4-cyanoisocoumarin (X) was similarly prepared by the action of diazomethane on 4-cyanoisocoumarin (IX).

This behaviour of diazomethane on the isocoumarin double bond caused hindrance in the synthesis of oosponol (XI), a natural product isolated from the culture filtrate of *Oospora astringens*¹¹ from 8-methoxyisocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid (XII) prepared from 7-methoxyindan-1-one (XX). However, Mori *et al.*¹⁰ were able to synthesise the oosponol diacetate in very poor yield (*ca.* 0.2%) from the acid chloride (XIII) by the action of controlled amount of diazomethane and decomposing the resulting oily diazoketone with acetic acid. They were able to isolate several other products including 3-methyl and 3,4-*endo*-methylene derivatives.

A different synthesis of 3-methylisocoumarins from homophthalic acids has been devised. The half-ester (XXII) of homophthalic acid, prepared by the partial hydrolysis of dimethyl homophthalate, was converted into its acid chloride and thence into the²corresponding diazoketone (XXIII). The diazoketone on heating with hydriodic acid gave (IV). Hydriodic acid acted as reducing agent in the conversion of diazoketone into methyl ketone^{12,13}

which spontaneously cyclised to 3-methylisocoumarin under acid conditions. 3-Methylisocoumarin prepared by this method was identical (IR) with 3-methylisocoumarin prepared earlier by the use of diazomethane.

8-Hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (XIV) is elaborated by the fungus *Marsmius ramealis*² and its structure has been confirmed by synthesis^{14,15}. A new synthesis involved in the partial hydrolysis of the dimethyl ester (XXV) prepared from 7-methoxyindan-1-one (XX) to give the half-ester (XXVI). The related diazoketone was refluxed with hydriodic acid for 3 hrs. to yield 8-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (XIV) identical with an authentic natural specimen kindly supplied by Dr. K. Mori.

3,4-Dimethylisocoumarin (XV), structurally related to oospolactone (XVI), a natural product isolated from the microorganism *Oospora*³ has also been similarly synthesised from α -methylhomophthalic acid (XXVIII) prepared by the nitrosation of 3-methylindan-1-one (XXI)¹⁶ and subsequent Beckmann transformation of the oxime with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride followed by hydrolysis of the resulting nitrile. The half-ester (XXIX), was converted to the related diazoketone (XXX) which with hot hydriodic acid gave 3,4-dimethylisocoumarin (XV).

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Methyl-4-methoxycarbonylisocoumarin (II): An ethereal suspension of isocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid (I; 0.6 g.) was added to ethereal diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethylurea (4.5 g.) and left in a refrigerator for 8 hr. The ether was removed under reduced pressure and the resulting product was decomposed by warming with acetic acid and then taken up in ether, washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and water respectively

and dried (MgSO_4). Removal of the solvent gave 3-methyl-4-methoxycarbonylisocoumarin (II; 0.5 g.) which was obtained as colourless rods, m.p. 95° from benzene-petroleum ether. (Found : C, 65.7; H, 5.0. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 66.0; H, 4.6%).

3-Methylisocoumarin (IV) : The foregoing ether (II; 2.5 g.) dissolved in a mixture of glacial acetic acid (6 ml.) and hydrochloric acid (6 ml.) was refluxed for 8.5 hr. Acetic acid was removed under reduced pressure and the residual mass dissolved in ether was extracted with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The extract was acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether, the extract washed with water and dried (MgSO_4). Evaporation of the solvent afforded a viscous oil which crystallised partly on keeping for two days and the solid was collected after trituration with ether. The solid (0.3 g.) so obtained was crystallised from benzene to give a compound, m.p. 179° identified as homophthalic acid (Found : C, 59.9; H, 4.6. Calc. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$: C, 60.0; H, 4.5%).

The residual oil which did not crystallise was decarboxylated by heating it with copper bronze in a metal bath at a temperature of 220° for 40 min. when carbon dioxide was lost. The residual mass was distilled and the distillate taken up in ether. The ether solution was washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution to remove any traces of acid and water and finally dried (MgSO_4). Removal of the solvent afforded 3-methylisocoumarin (IV; 0.1 g.) which crystallised from petroleum ether to provide colourless needles, m.p. 74° - 75° (lit.,⁵ m.p. 73° - 74°) (Found : C, 74.8; H, 5.3. Calc. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$: C, 75.0; H, 5.0%).

3-Methyl-4-(ω -acetoxyacetyl)isocoumarin (V) : An ethereal suspension of acid chloride prepared from isocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid (I; 1.2 g.) was added to dry ethereal diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethylurea (9 g.) and left overnight in a refrigerator. Ether was then removed under reduced pressure and the diazoketone (XVII; 1 g.) so obtained was crystallised from benzene to give straw yellow cubic crystals, m.p. 137° (decomp.). (Found : N, 21.6. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_3\text{N}_4$ requires : N, 21.9%).

The crystallised diazoketone (0.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (3 ml.) was warmed on water bath until the evolution of nitrogen ceased. It was extracted with ether, the extract washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and water respectively and dried (MgSO_4). Evaporation of the solvent gave 3-methyl-4-(ω -acetoxyacetyl)isocoumarin (V) as an oil which was distilled at 180° - 200° (bath temp.) and 0.1 mm pressure. (Found : C, 64.4; H, 4.9. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 64.6; H, 4.6%).

3-Methyl-4-(ω -hydroxyacetyl)isocoumarin (VI) : The diazoketone (XVII; 0.5 g.) in dioxan (5 ml.) was warmed on water bath with 2N H_2SO_4 (3 ml.) until evolution of nitrogen ceased and then heated a little on a microflame. The resulting solution was extracted with chloroform and working up in the usual manner, (VI) was obtained as an oil (0.3 g.) which was characterised as its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. It crystallised from acetic acid to give chocolate coloured bars, m.p. 216° (decomp.). (Found : C, 54.0; H, 3.2. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_7\text{N}_4$ requires : C, 54.3; H, 3.5%).

3-Methylisocoumarin-4-acetic Acid (VIII) : The diazoketone (XVII; 1 g.) in dry methanol (20 ml.) was heated on water bath; to it was added small amount of slurry of silver oxide (0.2 g.) in dry methanol (15 ml.) and stirred. As soon as the evolution of nitrogen

subsided, more of the silver oxide was introduced and this process was continued until all the slurry had been added. The mixture was then refluxed for 35 hrs. on water bath. Within this period about 0.8 g. of silver oxide was added in instalments. Then the mixture was treated with charcoal, filtered and solvent evaporated to give viscous oil (b.p. 190°–200°/1.5 m.m.) (Found : C, 67.1; H, 5.4. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires : C, 67.2; H, 5.2%).

The foregoing ester dissolved in a mixture of acetic acid (2 ml.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (1 ml.) was refluxed for 3 to 4 hrs. Acetic acid was removed under reduced pressure, the residue taken up in ether and extracted with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The extract was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed with a little water and dried ($MgSO_4$). Removal of ether furnished a gummy residue which after chromatography over silica gel using benzene as eluent, furnished the desired acid (VIII; 0.2 g.). Crystallisation from benzene afforded clusters of colourless needles, m.p. 140°–41°. (Found : C, 66.1; H, 4.2. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires : C, 66.0; H, 4.6%).

3-Methyl-4-cyanoisocoumarin (X) : An ethereal suspension of 4-cyanoisocoumarin (IX; 0.6 g.)¹⁷ was added to ethereal diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethylurea (3 g.) and left overnight in a refrigerator. Next day, ether was removed under reduced pressure and the residue decomposed by warming with acetic acid on water bath and worked up in the usual manner to yield *3-methyl-4-cyanoisocoumarin (X)*; 0.3 g.). Crystallisation from benzene provided colourless cubes, m.p. 142° (lit.¹⁸, m.p. 142°). (Found : C, 71.5; H, 4.0. Calc. for $C_{11}H_7O_2N$: C, 71.3; H, 3.8%).

3-Methylisocoumarin (IV) : The solution of the acid chloride prepared from 2-methoxycarbonylphenylacetic acid (XXIII; 0.8 g.) in ether was added to dry ethereal diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethylurea (3 g.) and left overnight in a refrigerator. Next day, ether was removed under reduced pressure and the residual oil was refluxed with hydriodic acid (3 ml.) for half an hour. The mixture was cooled, diluted with water and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution, sodium thiosulphate solution and water successively and dried ($MgSO_4$). Removal of solvent gave a thick oil which was distilled to give a solid (0.4 g.) crystallising from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether as colourless needles, m.p. 74° (lit.⁵, m.p. 73°–74°) identical with the product isolated earlier.

2-Nitroso-7-methoxyindan-1-one : To a cooled mixture of 7-methoxyindan-1-one (XXI)¹⁹ (18 g.) in minimum volume of methanol and concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 ml.), methyl nitrite gas was passed for 10 min. when the *2-nitroso-7-methoxyindan-1-one* (7 g.) slowly separated. It crystallised from acetic acid as light yellow needles, m.p. 191°–92°. (Found : N, 7.0. $C_{10}H_9O_3N$ requires : N, 7.3%).

3-Methoxyhomophthalic Acid (XXIV) : The foregoing nitroso compound (6 g.) dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide (30 ml.) was treated with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride at 50° with stirring and then heated to 80° for 15 min. After cooling, the solution was filtered off and then refluxed with more of sodium hydroxide (25 ml.; 10%) for 8 hr. After cooling, the solution was acidified and concentrated to half of its volume. *3-Methoxyhomophthalic acid (XXIV)*; 1.8 g.) separated in crystalline form. On recrystallisation from water, it was

obtained as colourless plates, m.p. 164°–65° (lit.¹⁴, m.p. 165°–66°). (Found : C, 57.0; H, 4.5. Calc. for C₁₀H₁₀O₅ : C, 57.1; H, 4.8%).

Dimethyl 3-methoxyhomophthalate (XXV) : The dimethyl ester was prepared by the esterification of the above homophthalic acid (1.7 g.) with ethereal diazomethane (from 8 g. of nitrosomethylurea). The ester distilled at 170°–75°/0.1 m.m. as a colourless oil (1.4 g.). (Found : C, 60.4; H, 5.6. C₁₂H₁₄O₅ requires : C, 60.5; H, 5.9%).

2-Methoxycarbonyl-3-methoxyphenylacetic Acid (XXVI) : Dimethyl 3-methoxyhomophthalate (XXV; 1.2 g.) was refluxed with methanolic potassium hydroxide (2.8 ml.; 10%) for 25 min. After removal of methanol under reduced pressure, the solution was cooled, diluted and acidified with hydrochloric acid when an oil separated which was extracted with ether, the extract washed with water and dried (MgSO₄). Evaporation of the solvent yielded 2-methoxycarbonyl-3-methoxyphenylacetic acid (XXVI; 0.8 g.) which was crystallised from benzene—petroleum ether to give colourless needles, m.p. 104° (lit.¹⁴, m.p. 106°–107°). (Found : C, 59.0; H, 5.2. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₂O₅ : C, 58.9; H, 5.4%). ν_{\max} . 1720 cm⁻¹ (ester carbonyl), 1696 cm⁻¹ (acid carbonyl).

8-Hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (XIV) : A solution of 2-methoxycarbonyl-3-methoxyphenylacetic acid (0.8 g.) in dry benzene (2 ml.) was treated with oxalyl chloride (1 ml.) in cold (10°) for half an hour and then kept at room temperature for 6 hr. The excess of oxalyl chloride was then removed under reduced pressure and the last traces removed by twice successive addition of benzene followed by its removal under reduced pressure. The resulting oily acid chloride in dry ether was added to dry ethereal diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethylurea (3 g.) and left overnight in a refrigerator. Next day, ether was removed under reduced pressure and diazoketone so obtained was refluxed with hydriodic acid (4.5 ml.) for 4 hr. Working up in the manner described for the preparation of (IV), 8-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (XIV; 0.3 g.) was obtained which on crystallisation from benzene gave colourless needles, m.p. 97°–98° identical with an authentic specimen kindly supplied by Dr. Mori¹⁴. ν_{\max} . 1682 cm⁻¹ (chelated carbonyl) and 3430 cm⁻¹ (chelated hydroxyl).

Methyl 8-methoxyisocoumarin-4-carboxylate : A mixture of dimethyl 3-methoxyhomophthalate (XXV; 1.2 g.), methyl formate (6 ml.) and dry sodium methoxide (derived from 0.3 g. of sodium) in dry ether (10 ml.) was kept at room temp. for 24 hr. The mixture was then refluxed with more methyl formate (2 ml.) for 2 hr. The mixture was treated with water, ether layer separated and the aqueous layer was acidified. It was taken up in ether. On evaporation of the solvent, the residual oil of *methyl 8-methoxyisocoumarin-4-carboxylate* separated as solid on cooling. On crystallisation from methanol it was obtained as colourless needles, m.p. 148°–49°. (Found : C, 61.3; H, 4.0. C₁₂H₁₀O₅ requires : C, 61.5; H, 4.3%).

8-Methoxyisocoumarin-4-carboxylic Acid (XII) : Methyl 8-methoxyisocoumarin-4-carboxylate (0.6 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of acetic acid (5 ml.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 ml.) for one and half hours during which time the *8-methoxyisocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid* separated in granular form. The solution was cooled, the acid filtered off and crystallised from acetic acid in fine needles, m.p. 254°–55° (Found : C, 59.8; H, 3.5. C₁₁H₈O₅ requires : C, 60.0; H, 3.7%).

8-Hydroxyisocoumarin-4-carboxylic Acid : 8-Methoxyisocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid (15 mg.) was heated with hydrobromic acid (0.05 ml.) in an oil bath at 50° for 2 hr. After working up in the usual manner, the oospoic acid (10 mg.), m.p. 246° (mixed m.p. undepressed with oospoic acid obtained from natural source) was obtained as colourless leaflets. It gave positive ferric reaction and identical IR spectrum with that of oospoic acid kindly supplied by Dr. K. Mori¹⁴.

α -Methylhomophthalic Acid (XXVIII) : 2-Nitroso-3-methylindan-1-one²⁰ (10 g.) dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide (50 ml.) was treated with *p*-toluene sulphonyl chloride (10.5 g.) at 60° with shaking during 1 hr. It was kept on water bath for an additional hour. The solution was refluxed with more sodium hydroxide (50 ml.; 10%) for 10 hr. On acidification α -methylhomophthalic acid was obtained which on crystallisation from chloroform yielded colourless plates, m.p. 151° (lit.²¹, m.p. 146°–47°).

2-Methoxycarbonyl- α -methylphenylacetic Acid (XXIX) : The foregoing homophthalic acid (XXVIII; 3.8 g.) was esterified with ethereal diazomethane (from 12 g. of nitrosomethylurea). The ester (2.8 g.) was refluxed with methanolic potassium hydroxide (7 ml.; 10%) for 40 min. After removal of methanol the solution was cooled, diluted and acidified to give (XXX; 1.2 g.) which crystallised from chloroform in colourless plates, m.p. 115°–16°. (Found : C, 63.2; H, 5.9. C₁₁H₁₂O₄ requires : C, 63.5; H, 5.8%). ν_{\max} . 1719 cm⁻¹ (ester carbonyl), 1695 cm⁻¹ (acid carbonyl).

3,4-Dimethylisocoumarin (XV) : A solution of the acid chloride prepared from (XXIX; 1 g.) by oxalyl chloride in the usual manner, in ether was treated with dry ethereal diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethylurea (3 g.) and left overnight in a refrigerator. Removal of ether under reduced pressure afforded oily diazoketone which was refluxed with hydriodic acid (5 ml.) for 2 hr. Working up in the manner described for the preparation of (XIV), 3,4-dimethylisocoumarin (0.5 g.) was obtained which crystallised from benzene in cream coloured prismatic bars, m.p. 128°–30° (lit.²², m.p. 129°). (Found : C, 75.5; H, 6.0. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₀O₂ : C, 75.8; H, 5.8%). ν_{\max} . 1720 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl).

Two of us (C.B. and T.R.V.) are indebted to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for the provision of Junior and Senior Research Fellowship respectively.

REFERENCES

1. L. A. Mitscher, W. W. Andres and W. McCrae, *Experientia*, 1964, **30**, 258.
2. G. Bendz, *Ark. Kemi. Min. Geol.*, 1959, **14**, 511; *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, **54**, 10056.
3. I. Yamamoto, *Agr. Biol. Chem.* (Tokyo), 1961, **25**, 400; *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, **55**, 23670.
4. S. Gabriel and A. Neumann, *Ber.*, 1892, **25**, 3563.
5. H. Nogami, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1941, **61**, 46; *Chem. Abs.*, 1941, **35**, 4764.
6. G. G. Smith, C. W. Delong, W. H. Wetzel and V. P. Murlidharan, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1967, **4**, 501.
7. R. B. Tirodkar and R. N. Usgaonkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 935.
8. L. F. Fieser and J. L. Hartwell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 1480.
9. J. Fried and R. C. Elderfield, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1941, **6**, 577.

10. M. Shiozaki, K. Mori and M. Matsui, *Agr. Biol. Chem.* (Tokyo), 1968, **32**, 42.
11. Y. Yamamoto, K. Nitta and Y. Yamamoto, *Agr. Biol. Chem.* (Tokyo), 1962, **26**, 486.
12. M. L. Wolform and R. L. Brown, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1516.
13. M. L. Wolform, D. I. Weisblat and S. W. Waisbrot, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 632.
14. M. Matsui, S. Arasaki and K. Mori, *Agr. Biol. Chem.* (Tokyo), 1964, **28**, 896.
15. J. Blair and G. T. Newbold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2871.
16. C. F. Koelsch, H. Hochmann and C. D. Le Claire, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 59.
17. J. N. Chatterjea, B. K. Banerji and N. Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **40**, 283.
18. F. Johnson and W. A. Nasutavicus, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 3953.
19. J. D. Loudon and R. K. Razdan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 4299.
20. J. V. Broun and G. Kirschbaum, *Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 3045.
21. S. Gabriel, *Ber.*, 1887, **20**, 2504.
22. G. Heller, *Ber.*, 1935, **68**, 1085.